

Metallic Cerium in Organic Synthesis.

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Since the middle of the nineteenth century various metals, *e.g.*, sodium, potassium, silver, zinc, copper, mercury, magnesium, aluminium, etc., have been used more or less successfully in organic synthesis, but the metal cerium which has been a chemical curiosity for quite a long time and whose commercial manufacture has been of comparatively very recent origin, has not received any application in organic synthesis upto this time. Consequently the present investigation was undertaken. Details of the successful experiments are given in the experimental part, while those of the unsuccessful attempts are omitted.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dry distillation with cerium powder.—In these experiments various organic compounds were submitted to dry distillation with cerium powder in a current of pure hydrogen in accordance with the method already described by Ray and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 103; *cf.* also Chakrabarty and Dutt, *ibid.*, p. 513). The results are summarised in the table below.

Substance.	Temperature of distillation.	Main product.	Yield.	By-products.
Pheno]	470°	benzene	39%	diphenyl
Resorcinol	500°-540°	..	42	phenol
Hydroquinone	..	..	40	..
Pyrogallol	..	..	27	phenol, catechol
α -Naphthol	..	naphthalene	60	nil
β -Naphthol	..	..	66	nil
α -Nitronaphthalene	..	α -naphthylamine	49	naphthalene
<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene	..	<i>p</i> -toluidine	33	toluene
Salicylic acid	..	benzene	51	phenol
Phthalic anhydride	dull red heat	phthalide	12	benzaldehyde
Benzoic acid	..	benzene	30	diphenyl

Substance.	Temperature of distillation.	Main product.	Yield.	By-products.
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	dull red heat	aniline	32%	<i>p</i> -aminophenol
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	„	„	37	<i>o</i> -aminophenol
Azobenzene	„	„	32	nil
Anthraquinone	„	anthracene	61	nil
Phenanthraquinone	„	phenanthrene	54	nil
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	400°	<i>p</i> -phenylenediamine	32	aniline
Benzophenone	„	diphenylmethane	59	nil
Thiodiphenylamine	dull red heat	carbazole	56	hydrogen sulphide

Friedel and Craft's Reaction with Cerium Powder.

Triphenylmethane from benzal chloride and benzene.—Benzene (18·7 g.), benzal chloride (8·6 g.) and cerium powder (5 g.) were refluxed together on a water-bath for 10 hours. The dark violet product was filtered from the excess of cerium and fractionated to remove benzene and benzal chloride. The solid residue crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 92° and was identified to be triphenylmethane, yield 1·2 g.

Triphenyl carbinol from benzoyl chloride and benzene.—A mixture of benzene (50 g.), benzoyl chloride (15 g.) and cerium powder (4 g.) was heated under reflux for 15 hours. Dark red product was fractionated as above and the fraction above 250° crystallised in yellow needles from alcohol, m. p. 160° and identified as triphenyl carbinol, yield 7·2 g.

Benzoylbenzoic acid from benzoyl chloride and benzoic acid.—Benzoyl chloride (7·5 g.), benzoic acid (6 g.) and cerium powder (4 g.) were refluxed at 160° for 12 hours. The dark violet product was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid and steam distilled until benzoic acid ceased to come over. The hot filtrate deposited needles of *o*-benzoylbenzoic acid on cooling, m. p. 128°, yield 5·1 g.

Triphenylchloromethane from benzotrichloride and benzene.—Benzotrichloride (6·3 g.), benzene (20 g.) and cerium powder (3 g.) were heated under reflux for 14 hours. The dark red product was fractionated at 15 mm. from an oil-bath at 150° until nothing further distilled over. The solid residue crystallised from carbon disulphide in pale yellow prisms, m. p. 106° and was identified to be triphenylchloromethane, yield 1·5 g.

Diphenyl from benzene and bromobenzene.—Benzene (12 g.), bromobenzene (8.5 g.) and cerium powder (4 g.) on refluxing for 20 hours gave very feeble reaction. The yield of diphenyl isolated on fractionation was only 0.25 g., m. p. 68°.

Diphenyl from chlorobenzene and benzene.—Reaction was carried on as above. Yield of diphenyl from 11 g. of chlorobenzene was only 0.3 g.

Diphenyl from iodobenzene and benzene.—Reaction was carried on as above. Yield of diphenyl from 8.1 g. of iodobenzene was only 0.22 g.

Triphenylmethane from benzene and chloroform.—Benzene (18 g.), chloroform (18 g.) and cerium powder (4 g.) were refluxed for 12 hours. The dark violet product was fractionated first at ordinary pressure and then at 8 mm. over naked flame. The last product solidified on cooling and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 92° and identified to be triphenylmethane, yield 2.6 g.

Anthraquinone from benzene and phthalyl chloride.—Phthalyl chloride (10 g.), benzene (12 g.) and cerium powder (4 g.) were refluxed at 170-80° for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid to remove cerium and with dilute caustic soda to remove phthalic acid. The benzene was distilled off and residual anthraquinone crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 276°, yield 3.5 g.

Benzylidene acetophenone from benzal chloride and acetophenone.—A mixture of acetophenone (3 g.), benzal chloride (4 g.) and cerium (1.2 g.) when refluxed at 180-200° for 4 hours gave a very vigorous reaction and the product on alcohol extraction yielded a crystalline solid. It was recrystallised from ligroin and identified as benzylidene acetophenone, m. p. 57°, yield 3 g.

Zincke's Reaction with Cerium Powder.

Diphenylmethane from benzyl chloride and benzene.—Benzene (38.5 g.), benzyl chloride (20 g.) and cerium (5.2 g.) were refluxed for 10 hours. The dark red product was filtered, washed with water, dried and fractionated. The fraction between 250-80° (11.2 g. redistilled at 260-62°) was collected and identified to be diphenylmethane. Lower fractions contained benzene and benzyl chloride and the higher fractions triphenylmethane and *sym*-tetraphenylethane, (4.2 g. and 1.5 g. respectively).

Phenyltolylmethane and dibenzyltoluene from benzyl chloride and toluene.—A mixture of benzyl chloride (25.8 g.), toluene (34 g.) and cerium (6 g.) was refluxed at 110-20° for 10 hours. The product was purified and fractionated as above. The fraction at 260-85° (redistilled at 275-82° and then again at 279-80°) was identified to be phenyltolylmethane (yield 23.1 g.) and that above 310° (subsequently redistilled at 390-98°) as dibenzyltoluene (12.4 g.).

Anisoylphenylmethane from anisol and benzyl chloride.—Anisol (22 g.), benzyl chloride (21 g.) and cerium powder (5 g.) were refluxed at 110-20° for 8 hours. The mixture was purified and fractionated as above. The fraction at 300-15° (redistilled at 305-10°) was identified to be anisoylphenylmethane *i.e.* *p*-methoxydiphenylmethane (yield 18.8 g.) and the fraction at 378-80° (9.2 g.) was most probably dibenzylanisol but could not be identified for want of accurate information.

Phenetoylphenylmethane from phenetol and benzyl chloride.—A mixture of phenetol (20.4 g.), benzyl chloride (18.2 g.) and cerium (5 g.) were treated as above, and the reaction product similarly fractionated. The fraction at 312-45° (redistilled at 338-41°) was identified to be *p*-ethoxydiphenylmethane (yield 26.8 g.). The dark red residue in the distilling flask crystallised from alcohol in bright yellow plates, m. p. 57° and was probably dibenzylphenetol, but could not be identified for want of data (yield 2.1 g.).

Benzylquinol dimethyl ether from benzyl chloride and quinol dimethyl ether.—Quinol dimethyl ether (14 g.), benzyl chloride (10 g.) and cerium (5 g.) were refluxed at 120-30° for 10 hours. The product was purified and fractionated as above and the fraction at 345-60° (redistilled at 354-56°) identified as benzylquinol dimethyl ether, yield 14.2 g.

p-Benzylphenol from benzyl chloride and phenol.—Benzyl chloride (16 g.), phenol (21 g.) and cerium (6.2 g.) were heated at 70° for ½ hour and then at 120-30° for 6 hours. Reaction was very vigorous. The product was purified and fractionated as above. The fraction at 310-30° (redistilled at 320-22°) was identified as *p*-benzylphenol (yield 27.6 g.) and the fraction at 360-70° (redistilled at 365-67°) which was free from phenolic group was identified as *p*-benzylphenol benzyl ether, $C_6H_5CH_2 \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot O \cdot CH_2C_6H_5$, yield 3.2 g.

Acetophenone from acetyl chloride and benzene.—Benzene (16 g.), acetyl chloride (1.2 g.) and cerium (4 g.) when refluxed for 6 hours gave a very vigorous reaction. The product was treated with ice-cold

hydrochloric acid and the resulting yellow oil washed, dried and fractionated. The fraction at 185°-210° (redistilled at 198-200°) was identified as acetophenone, yield 12.2 g.

Benzophenone from benzoyl chloride and benzene.—On refluxing a mixture of benzoyl chloride (10.2 g.), benzene (15 g.) and cerium (3.5 g.) for 12 hours, the product was filtered, washed with strong caustic soda and water, dried and fractionated. The fraction at 300-15° solidified in the receiver and after recrystallisation from alcohol (m. p. 47°) it was identified as benzophenone, yield 2.9 g.

Reformatski's Reaction with Cerium Powder.

A mixture of acetophenone (12 g.), ethyl chloroacetate (12 g.), cerium (10 g.) and dry benzene (70 g.) was refluxed with the addition of a minute crystal of iodine for 2 hours. Reaction was very vigorous. The product was treated with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid, washed with sodium hydroxide and water, dried and fractionated at 5 mm. The fraction at 112-30° (redistilled at 118-20°) was identified as β -phenylmethylhydroxypropionic ester, yield 6.1 g.

The above reaction was tried with ethyl bromoacetate instead of ethyl chloroacetate, yield 9.3 g.

Ullmann's Reaction with Cerium Powder.

Diethyl succinate from ethyl chloroacetate and ethyl acetate.—A mixture of ethyl chloroacetate (12 g.), ethyl acetate (10 g.) and cerium (8 g.) was refluxed at 110-20° for 12 hours and the product filtered, washed, dried and fractionated. The fraction at 200-20° (redistilled at 216-18°) was identified as diethyl succinate, yield 3.8 g.

Adipic acid from β -iodopropionic acid.—When β -iodopropionic acid (5 g.) was heated with cerium (8 g.) at 160-70° for 3 hours much iodine liberated. The product was extracted with hot water and the aqueous solution on concentration gave adipic acid crystal, m.p. 148°, yield 0.7 g.

Diphenyl from bromobenzene.—Bromobenzene (8 g.) and cerium (12 g.) were refluxed at 170-80° for 20 hours. The product was filtered and fractionated. The fraction at 240-60° (redistilled at 252-54°) solidified on cooling and recrystallised from ether, m.p. 70°, and was identified as diphenyl, yield 0.75 g.

Diphenyl from (i) iodobenzene and (ii) chlorobenzene.—Procedure was same as above, yields of diphenyl isolated, 0.5 g. from (i) and 0.28 g. from (ii).

Diphenyl ether from phenol and bromobenzene.—A mixture of phenol (9.5 g.), bromobenzene (17 g.), cerium (5 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.5 g.) was refluxed at 180-200° for 10 hours. The filtered product was steam distilled and the distillate was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with dilute caustic soda and water, dried and fractionated. The fraction at 240-63° (redistilled at 253-54°) was identified as diphenyl ether, yield 3.5 g.

Diphenylamine from aniline and bromobenzene.—Aniline (12 g.), bromobenzene (16 g.) and cerium (3 g.) were refluxed at 180-200° for 10 hours. The filtered product was fractionated and the fraction at 300-20° solidified, and recrystallised from alcohol, m. p. 52°, and identified as diphenylamine, yield 2.8 g.

Succinic acid from chloroacetic and acetic acids.—A mixture of sodium chloroacetate (11.5 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (8 g.) and cerium (4 g.) when heated at 110-20° for 1 hour gave a very vigorous reaction. The product was extracted with water and ammonia added in slight excess to precipitate ceric hydroxide. The boiled and neutral filtrate was treated with ferric chloride when ferric succinate was precipitated. This was decomposed in aqueous suspension by hydrogen sulphide and from the filtrate succinic acid was extracted with ether, m.p. 185°, yield 2.9 g.

Neutral Reduction with Cerium Powder.

Picramic acid and triaminophenol from picric acid.—Picric acid (10 g.) in alcohol (70 p.c.) containing ammonium chloride (4.5 g.) was vigorously shaken with cerium powder (25 g.) in a shaking machine. After 10 hours the product was completely reduced and yielded 63 p.c. of triaminophenol. After 5 hours the product consisted of a mixture of picramic acid (85 p.c.) and triaminophenol (5 p.c.).

Sulphanilic acid and dimethylaniline from methyl orange.—Methyl orange (6.5 g.), water (1500 c.c.), cerium (15 g.) and ammonium chloride (3.5 g.) were shaken together for 3 hours. The product resolved into sulphanilic acid (2.1 g.) and dimethylaniline (1.9 g.) with complete reduction.

o-Aminophenol from o-nitrophenol.—*o*-Nitrophenol on similar treatment as above yielded *o*-aminophenol (79 p.c.).

Benzhydrol from benzophenone.—Benzophenone (6 g.), alcohol (150 c.c., 70 p.c.), ammonium chloride (3 g.) and cerium (6 g.)

were shaken for 20 hours. 5.4 G. of benzhydrol (m.p. 66°) were obtained.

Aniline from nitrobenzene.—Nitrobenzene (6 g.), ammonium chloride (0.5 g.), water (100 c.c.) and cerium (16 g.) were shaken for 4 hours, then warmed on the water-bath for 1 hour with addition of more cerium (12 g.). Yield of aniline 3.5 g.

p-Toluidine from nitrotoluene.—*p*-Nitrotoluene on similar treatment as above yielded *p*-toluidine (66 p.e.).

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